

DAMAGE IN BIAxIAL FATIGUE OF COMPOSITES

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Summary

An experimental investigation was performed of damage in fiber-reinforced composites due to biaxial fatigue. Damage was estimated by measurement of specimen compliance in bending as well as of fracture toughness and Charpy energy. It was shown that these parameters depend on the number of cycles in fatigue and also on the stresses. If the two loads are out of phase, damage may increase more rapidly than otherwise. A simple model based on arrays of cracks and the growth of these cracks is proposed for predicting the effect of the number of fatigue cycles on compliance and stress-intensity factor. It is suggested that the damage concept should be used for engineering applications in design.

Introduction

Accumulation of damage occurs in any material subjected to a cyclic stress of sufficiently high amplitude. The concept of damage has been successfully utilized in certain engineering applications for design against fatigue of components and structures. It has also some physical relevance and can be related to the micromechanical behaviour of materials during fatigue. For example, damage can be correlated with the deformation and growth of voids in ductile metals or with fiber breakage and matrix cracking in composites.

Multiaxial states of stress are frequently encountered in engineering components. In designing these against yielding under static loads, the multiaxiality is given due consideration. In designing against fatigue, however, it is still common practice to employ uni-axial theory to a large extent. Biaxial fatigue has been studied for a long time, but still the results of these studies have received rather little attention in engineering applications.

Through use of theories for biaxial fatigue, attempts are made to predict biaxial behaviour using data from uni-axial fatigue tests.

As was convincingly shown in 1984 by Miller and Brown (1), this prediction is sometimes unreliable for isotropic materials. It becomes even more questionable to use in materials which exhibit large

directional dependence of mechanical properties as many composites do.

For example, one parameter used for predicting fatigue life is the octaheder shear stress as shown in 1985 by Ohlson (2) which is a vectorial quantity. Its range varies with the direction in the material. The maximum range is considered critical for the occurrence of fatigue failure in isotropic materials. In a composite the anisotropy of mechanical properties tends to make this parameter less significant for predicting fatigue life. Instead, the damage approach becomes attractive, as it can be applied to any material regardless of anisotropy.

Even though valuable information is lost by using a scalar quantity such as damage for characterizing biaxial fatigue, one instead obtains a quantity which is more easily handled in engineering design. Besides, the concept can be extended for taking directional dependence into account if desired.

Aim of investigation

For the purpose of monitoring fatigue damage in experiments, one may measure some physically significant property which can be correlated with damage, like damping, mechanical compliance, fracture toughness, or Charpy energy.

In the present study, the latter three properties were recorded on specimens which have been subjected to fatigue loading.

Experimental procedure

Fatigue

Experiments were performed in a specially designed testing machine where the specimen is simultaneously loaded in torsion and bending. The amplitudes of the loads as well as the phase angle between them may be set at determined values independently. In principle, this enables one to examine critically proposed theories of biaxial fatigue. As was convincingly shown in literature, experimental evidence to these theories is still to a large extent lacking, particularly for the case of out-of-phase loading as shown in 1983 by Smith and Pascoe (3).

Determination of compliance

The specimens were then removed from the fatigue testing machine and inserted into a conventional servo-hydraulic tensile testing machine. The compliance of the specimen in various directions during bending was determined. If required, the moduli of the material may be evaluated from the compliance as shown in 1982 by Poursatip, Ashby and Beaumont (4). After this measurement is made, specimens may be reinserted into the biaxial fatigue testing machine for continuing the fatigue process.

Determination of notch sensitivity

Certain specimens were equipped with a sharp notch, after they had been run in fatigue. The fracture toughness of the material was then determined in the tensile testing machine, utilizing an experimental technique which is well established in fracture mechanics.

As notch sensitivity of materials is often expressed in terms of energy absorption in a drop-weight hammer test, it was decided that this type of experiments should also be performed on the specimens which had been subjected to fatigue damage, for the purpose of comparison with results in literature.

The advantage of making drop-weight hammer tests in their experimental simplicity in comparison with fracture toughness testing. On the other hand, complications in the interpretation of results may arise due to wave reflection phenomena and strain rate effects.

Since both the experimental procedures for determining notch sensitivity are destructive by nature, interest was focused on the compliance method which can be used for continuous observation of damage development throughout the fatigue test.

Materials

The materials under investigation were a carbon-fiber reinforced epoxy (CFRP) and a glass-fiber reinforced polyester (GFRP). Two-ply laminates (-45° , $+45^\circ$ to the specimen axis) as well as laminates with all the fibers running in the axial direction were tested.

The phase angle varied between 0° and 180° . In most experiments the maximum principal stresses due to bending and due to torsion were of the same order of magnitude.

Results

The results show that there is a considerable decrease in bending compliance as well as in fracture toughness and Charpy energy for both materials as a function of the number of cycles in fatigue (fig. 1). A very strong dependence of the stress amplitude is observed. Effective stress according to von Mises was used for the representation of stress amplitude influence (in-phase loading). For small amplitudes, no damage was noticed which may be considered as an indication of the existence of a fatigue limit or a fatigue threshold.

Figure 1 - Reduction of relative compliance C/C_0 (fig. 1a), relative fracture toughness K_{IC}/K_{IC0} (1b) and relative Charpy energy U/U_0 (1c) with the number of cycles N in fatigue. The material tested was CFRP.

Figure 2 - Residual fracture toughness of CFRP after 10^6 c. as a function of the phase angle between loads in biaxial fatigue.

All the three parameters under study (compliance C , fracture toughness K_{IC} and Charpy energy U) were plotted as dimensionless quantities (C/C_0 , K_{IC}/K_{IC0} and U/U_0 , where index "o" denotes the virginal state) in fig. 1. The reduction of these quantities with the number of cycles is virtually the same. This may seem somewhat surprising but may be explained by a simple model of the effect of material deterioration on the parameters mentioned, as will be described below. The similarity in behaviour can be considered as a justification of the introduction of the damage concept for characterizing fatigue.

The most remarkable observation as to the effect of the phase angle between loads is that the damage displays a maximum for a value of 90° , fig. 2. This also agrees well with results from biaxial fatigue experiments on an aluminium alloy, made in 1985 by Ohlson (2) which show that fatigue life has a minimum for this phase angle.

Even although the damage concept seems particularly suitable for an engineering treatment of fatigue in composite materials it also has certain limitations. Among these may be mentioned the difficulty in defining the state of the material that corresponds to the damage approaching unity.

The results of the described experiments may also be used for representation of fatigue failure curves in a diagram where two principal stresses are plotted along the coordinate axes, fig. 3. Similar biaxial tests were performed in 1978 by G C Eckold, D Leadbetter, P D Soden & P R Griggs (5). These plots lend themselves to immediate use for structural design.

Micro-mechanical model for estimating fatigue damage in a fiber-reinforced composite.

Consider the simple case of infinite arrays of cracks perpendicular to the tensile stress σ , fig. 4. These cracks develop in fatigue and may be caused by local delamination between fiber and matrix due to shear.

The length of each crack is $2a$, the distance between their centres in one array is $2W$ and the distance between parallel arrays is $2W$. In plane stress the compliance C in uniaxial tension perpendicular to the array of cracks may be expressed as

Figure 3 - Fatigue failure curves in the principal stress plane recorded for CFRP.

Figure 4 - Micro-mechanical model of a ply containing arrays of cracks, used for estimating C and K_I .

Figure 5 - Specimen compliance in uniaxial tension C as a function of a/W , predicted by the model shown in fig. 4.

Figure 6 - Stress-intensity factor at the crack tips K_I as a function of a/W , predicted by the model shown in fig. 4.

$$C = \frac{1}{tE} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot g\left(\frac{a}{W}\right) \right], \quad (1)$$

t being the thickness of the ply, E the modulus of elasticity of the matrix and g a function which is tabulated in literature. The graph of C as a function of a/W is given in fig. 5. This compliance holds for a single array of cracks. For a specimen with N_1 arrays of cracks the compliance is $N_1 C$.

The stress intensity factor at the crack tip in an array may also be calculated from literature, as shown in 1973 by M Isida (6) through use of the formula

$$K_I = \sigma\sqrt{a} \cdot h\left(\frac{a}{W}\right) \quad (2)$$

This function was plotted in fig. 6.

It is realized that C as well as K_I are similarly shaped functions of a/W over a limited range of a/W. Hence, it may be permitted to define the damage D as either of D_C or D_K :

$$D_C = (C/C_0)^{\beta_c} \quad (3a)$$

or

$$D_K = \left(\frac{K_I \sigma_0}{K_{IC} \sigma} \right)^{\beta_k} \quad (3b)$$

σ_0 being the stress which implies crack initiation in the virgin material whose fracture toughness is K_{IC} , β_c and β_k being material constants which may be determined by experiments. In eq. (3b), K_I was divided by the applied tensile stress σ , for the purpose of making D_K dependent of crack length only.

For introducing the damage rate as a function of the number of fatigue cycles N one may apply Paris' law for fatigue crack propagation, assuming equal propagation of all the crack tips

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C_1 \cdot (\Delta K_I)^n, \quad (4)$$

ΔK_I being the stress-intensity factor range, C_1 and n material constants. Through use of ref. (6), eq. (4) can be integrated over any interval of crack length. A simplification is obtained in the following way.

As seen from fig. 6, $K_I(a/W)$ may be approximated by a linear function within a small range of a/W, hence

$$\Delta K_I = \sigma\sqrt{W} \cdot \alpha a \quad (5)$$

α being a factor of proportionality.

From eq. (4) one has

$$\frac{da}{a^n} = dN \cdot \alpha^n \cdot C_1 \quad (6)$$

Upon integration from the initial crack length a_0 one obtains

$$a = (\Delta N \cdot \alpha \cdot C_1^n + a_0^{-n+1}) \frac{1}{-n+1} \quad (7)$$

According to (3b) this yields

$$D_K = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{K_{IC}} \alpha \right)^{\beta_k} \cdot (\Delta N \cdot \alpha \cdot C_1^n + a_0^{-n+1}) \frac{\beta_k}{-n+1} \quad (8)$$

This equation constitutes a relation between the damage D and the number of cycles in fatigue ΔN . Introducing new constants, eq. (8) may be re-written on the form

$$D_K = (\Delta N \cdot k_1 + k_2)^{k_3} \quad (9)$$

These constants can be determined through identification with fig. 1b.

Conclusions

The present investigation shows that it is possible to obtain a very close fit between experiments and theoretical prediction of damage according to eq. (3) and eq. (9). The concept of fatigue damage can be used for engineering design purpose for composites. Biaxial problems can be conveniently treated in the same manner. The occurrence of a more rapidly increasing damage in out-of-phase loading should be given appropriate attention.

References

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